

Implementation and Comparative Analysis of Security Algorithms for Big Data Security in Cloud Computing

Renu Yadav, Dr. Abid Hussain

¹Research Scholar, School of Computer Application & Technology, Career Point University, Kota, (Rajasthan), Email: renu.mca1985@gmail.com

²Associate Professor, School of Computer Application, Career Point University, Kota, (Rajasthan), Email: abid.hussain@cpur.edu.in

ABSTRACT

Big data security has faced new challenges as an outcome of the significant growth in the use of cloud computing for big data processing and storage recently. Effective security actions are now important because of the increasing acceptance of cloud services for the storage and processing of immense volumes of data. Many security algorithms have been created and put into use to overcome these issues. To improve large data security in cloud computing environment, this paper compares and implements security techniques. Our main objective is to assess the productivity and effectiveness of various encryption algorithms in protecting large amounts of data stored on cloud servers. Through feasible research and experimentation, we demonstrate how encryption will function both during the transfer of data to the cloud and during its resting and utilization. We also select the optimal approaches for providing robust security in big data applications hosted on the cloud.

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1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Big Data

Big Data means the large amount of data that are generated from different sources like a machine, internet, social networks, traditional business systems, and from the Internet of Things. Format of data can be structured, semi-structured, or unstructured, or any combination of these varieties. Big data is often described as five Vs: Volume, Velocity,

Variety, Veracity, and Value. Volume refers to the amount of data, which define to be in the range or size of datasets to be considered big data. Variety denotes the problem of big data being able to consist of different formats of data, such as text, numbers, videos, and images. Velocity represents the speed at which the data grows, that is, at what speed new data is generated. Furthermore, veracity concerns the accuracy and trustworthiness of data. Lastly, value corresponds to the usefulness of data, indicating that some data points, or a combination of points, maybe more valuable than others. Data process can be defined as data-at-rest, data-in-transit, and data-in-use. Analyzing large amounts of data using a variety of data types to uncover hidden patterns, undiscovered connections, market trends, customer needs, and future suggestions is known as big data analytics. This technique aids in making important decisions. Big Data analysis aids in both comprehending the facts found in the data and locating the information most crucial to the company and upcoming choices [1] [2].

1.2 Need of Cloud Computing for Big Data

Cloud computing states to the transfer of computing service for instance servers, storage, databases, networking, software, and analyticover the internet to offer faster, flexible resources, and scalable. To manage, store, and process big data everywhere and every time created a new challenge. Big data need to find better methods to process and analyze, it requires infrastructure, more capacity warehouse, and more servers to the rapidly increasing data. For this purpose, cloud computing comes to help, where big data organizations move their data to the cloud. Cloud computing efficiently offers infrastructure, administration, cost-effectiveness, and remote access from any location in the globe with an internet connection. Cloud computing can handle all 5V aspects that are related to big data. Large pools of computer resources are used to process volume; elasticity and on-demand features manage data velocity; and self-service, pooled resources, and elasticity handle a range of data kinds.

The veracity of the data relieved by self-service to select the best-matched services and pay-as-you-go cost model and value represented as accurate data, justifiable cost, and customer satisfaction with on-demand, elasticity features of cloud computing. Therefore, cloud computing not only provides facilities for the computation and processing of big data but also serves as a service model. However, Security issues are one in all the key challenges facing big data where the organization store and process a large amount of sensitive and confidential data to the cloud service providers.

A. Key Characteristics

On-demand self-service:Users can allocate computer resources as required using on-demand self-service.

Broad network access:Network services are accessible through conventional procedures and are made available on a wide scale.

Resource pooling: Resource pooling is a technique wherein various physical and virtual resources are dynamically allotted to accommodate the needs of several users.

Rapid elasticity:Accelerated elasticity refers to the capacity to rapidly modify resources in accordance with demand.

Measured service: Cloud systems employ utilisation metrics to measure and optimise resource usage, hence offering transparency to both consumers and providers.

B. Service Models:

Infrastructure as a Service (IaaS):Virtualized computing resources are made available via the internet by Infrastructure as a Service (IaaS).

Platform as a Service (PaaS):Platform as a Service, or PaaS, offers a platform so users don't have to worry about infrastructure; they can create, execute, and maintain applications.

Software as a Service (SaaS):Software as a Service, or SaaS, is a subscription-based online software delivery model[3].

1.3 Importance of Big Data Security in Cloud Environment

These are some notable threats and challenges that come with moving large amounts of data via cloud computing:

Data Breach:Data breaches can occur when unauthorized access to confidential information occurs during transit, allowing attackers to obtain valuable information through transmission flaws or intercepting data streams.

Man-in-The Middle(MitM) attacks:MitM attacks, which involve listening in on conversations and altering them, can threaten the integrity and confidentiality of large data by altering it during transmission.

Denial-of-Service(DoS) attack:Denial-of-service (DoS) incidents target communication channels or cloud infrastructure, preventing authorized individuals from accessing large amounts of data by overloading network resources, causing service interruptions and downtime.

Data Loss:Data transmission disruptions or data corruption can lead to loss of crucial information, affecting the reliability and confidentiality of large cloud data transfers.

Insider Threats:Data transmission risks hacking or insider attacks, with authorized individuals potentially violating rights to extract, break down, or manipulate important data.

Lack of End-to-End Encryption:Data transfer can be susceptible to illegal access or interception due to inadequate encryption measures, compromising confidentiality and integrity[4].

1.4 Mitigation Techniques and its importance for Big Data security

Transferring big data over the cloud presents various threats and challenges that organizations need to address to ensure the confidentiality, integrity, and availability of their data.Encryption techniques can be used to successfully reduce a number of the threat associated with transmitting huge volumes of data via the cloud. Following are the security measures assist in mitigating the threats and challenges that have been identified[5][6].

A. Encryption Algorithms

Encryption can encrypt big data during transit, ensuring that only authorized parties with the can access the data. Organizations can protectfrom unauthorized access and interception, mitigating the risk of data breaches, data snooping, and unauthorized data access during transfer over the cloud.A unique hash value may be generated for each data packet using hashing methods like SHA-256 (Secure Hash Algorithm 256-bit), which allows recipients to confirm the integrity of the data is being delivered. Any unauthorised changes or modification of data during transit can be detected using hash values. Hashing efforts can be detected by receivers since even little modifications to the data will produce distinct hash values.It can be used to check data integrity during transmission and at rest.By encrypting data transfers and authenticating communication partners, TLS/SSL protocols offer safe channels of communication between clients and cloud servers. Data is shielded against interception and eavesdropping during transit by end-to-end encryption, which it ensures[7] Furthermore, to protect against unauthorised access and man-in-the-middle attacks, TLS/SSL protocols validate the identity of all communication associates.TLS/SSL protocols secure data transfer over networks by encrypting data, ensuring confidentiality.

B. Identity and Access Management

Securing sensitive data during processing may be ensured by putting strong access control and authentication methods in place. This way, only authorised persons or processes can access the data. Access to data-in-use may be restricted and security regulations can be enforced with the use of fine-grained access controls, multi-factor authentication (MFA), and role-based access control (RBAC).This layered approach to data security contributes to an

all-encompassing protection against a range of threats and vulnerabilities. It uses TLS/SSL to ensure the secrecy and integrity of data while it is being sent, encryption to safeguard data while it is at rest, and hashing algorithms to confirm the integrity of the data[8].

C. Centralized Key Management System

Centralized key management system is a crucial aspect of encryption, ensuring the secure creation, storage, distribution, and management of encryption keys. It emphasizes key rotation to prevent manipulation threats and robust access restrictions to prevent unauthorized access. Large amounts of data might be encryption both in transit and at rest by enterprises using centralized key management systems, which ensures data security, availability, and integrity for data handled and preserved in the cloud. To avoid unwanted manipulation of data, the system creates and maintains keys for encryption. A centralized key management system ensures the safe transmission, maintenance, and management of encryption keys, strengthening the complete safety of big data over the cloud[9].

1. RELATED WORK

Wu et al. (2015) highlighted the evolving challenges of big data security in cloud computing, emphasizing the need for robust encryption and authentication mechanisms[10]. **Wang et al. (2016)** presented security and privacy issues in Big Data as a review. This thorough analysis encompasses a wide range of large data security and privacy issues, including those unique to cloud computing environments. regarding order to secure huge data on the cloud, it looks into privacy-preserving algorithms, access control systems, and encryption approaches[11]. Studies by **Liu et al. (2016)** investigated the implementation and performance of AES in securing big data stored and processed in cloud environments. Literature by **Li et al. (2016)** examined the usage and security properties of SHA-2 for data integrity verification and authentication in cloud computing[12]. A study by **Zhang et al. (2017)** examined emerging threats and vulnerabilities in cloud-based big data systems, underscoring the importance of implementing effective security algorithms[13]. **Kim et al. (2017)** compared the performance and security of different encryption algorithms, including AES, RSA, and ChaCha20-Poly1305, in securing big data in cloud environments[14]. Research by **Sharma et al. (2018)** evaluated the effectiveness of RSA for key management and digital signatures in cloud-based big data applications[15]. **Alam et al. (2018)** suggested a survey of security issues in big data. This survey throws light on the security issues regarding large data processing in cloud systems. It addresses potential mitigation techniques, new developments in big data security, and dangers including insider

attacks, data breaches, and unauthorised access[16].**Sharma et al.(2019)** stated that big data security and privacy issues in cloud computing. This study investigates the privacy and security issues that arise when big data and cloud computing collide. It looks at data availability, integrity, and confidentiality challenges, emphasising the value of access control, authentication, and encryption techniques in protecting large data in the cloud[17].**Zhang et al.(2020)** introduced a survey on security and privacy issues in big data. With an emphasis on the implications of security and privacy concerns in big data for cloud computing settings, this survey offers a thorough review of the subject. It addresses issues including identity theft, data leaks, and regulatory compliance in addition to possible fixes and future prospects for research[18].According to **Mishra et al. (2021)** data encryption, safe data exchange, and threat detection as security issues related to large data processing in cloud environments. It talks about how artificial intelligence and machine learning methods might improve cloud big data security [19]. **Zhao et al. (2021)** conducted comparative analyses of cryptographic hash functions, such as SHA-2 and SHA-3, to assess their suitability for data integrity protection and authentication in cloud-based big data systems[20]. **Liu, Y., Zhang, L., & Yu, S. (2022)** explained a Machine Learning Based Resource Management Framework for Big Data Analytics in Cloud Computing and managed the security and reliability through ML Algorithms [21]. **Wu, Z., Wang, L., & Li, W. (2022)** proposed a model for Micro Services Architecture to Enhance Reliability in Cloud-Based Big Data Systems [22]. **Zhang, J., Zhang, H., & Chen, J. (2023)** presented a detailed explanation about the Hardware Acceleration for Big Data Analytics in Cloud Computing [23]. **Wang, X., Zhang, W., & Guo, L. (2023)** explained the Secure Multi-party Computation for Privacy-Preserving Big Data Analytics in Cloud Computing [24]. **Choi, H., Park, S., & Kim, Y. (2023)** designed a Secure and Efficient Big Data Processing Framework for Cloud Computing Environments [25] for providing better security for the data management on cloud data center and prevent the unauthorized access.

2. IMPLEMENTATION

To provide robust and strong security mechanism we have used the various techniques. To extract the encryption/decryption time we write a python code for different size of data for instance 1,10, 20, 40,100MB shown below. We are utilizing the chacha20-poly1305 symmetric encryption and also compare it with another symmetric encryption(Blowfish,AES-128,192,256) for performance and reliability. To calculate its encryption, decryption time and

throughput we compared them using a range of data sizes, including 1MB, 10MB, 20MB, 40MB, and 100MB. When it comes to security and performance, we used to emphasise encryption. Undoubtedly, the typical time required for encryption and decryption can differ based on that specific processing task and several additional variables like the complex structure of the encryption algorithm, the volume of data being handled, the system's hardware capacity. For throughput and encryption/decryption time are two metrics that may be used to evaluate performance when it comes to encryption and decryption techniques.

A. Encryption Time

Encryption time is the time it takes to encrypt data, while average encryption time measures the time it takes to encrypt multiple data items or perform encryption operations on a dataset. This provides a comprehensive view of the overall performance impact of encryption, especially in applications where data confidentiality is a priority, such as secure messaging or data storage.

Table.1 Encryption Time Table

Data Size	Blowfish	AES-128	AES-192	AES-256	Chacha-20	Chacha20-poly1305
1MB	0.00003	0.00000045	0.0000004	0.00000035	0.00011	0.00000146667
10MB	0.00292	0.00010918	0.0001026	0.00011195	0.0005	0.00022335
20MB	0.00363	0.00019098	0.0001953	0.00020033	0.00125	0.00043486667
40MB	0.00691	0.00043712	0.0004358	0.00044995	0.00286	0.00088101667
100MB	0.02920	0.00209363	0.0022222	0.00211538	0.00292	0.00183055

```
import timeit

from cryptography.hazmat.primitives import serialization

from cryptography.hazmat.primitives.asymmetric import x25519

from cryptography.hazmat.primitives.asymmetric.ed25519 import Ed25519PrivateKey

from cryptography.hazmat.primitives.kdf.pbkdf2 import PBKDF2HMAC

from cryptography.hazmat.primitives import hashes

from cryptography.hazmat.primitives import padding

from cryptography.hazmat.primitives.ciphers.aead import ChaCha20Poly1305

def measure_chacha20_poly1305_encryption_decryption_time():

    key = get_random_bytes(32)

    data = get_random_bytes(1024)

    cipher = ChaCha20Poly1305(key)

    nonce = get_random_bytes(12)

    start_time = timeit.default_timer()

    ciphertext = cipher.encrypt(nonce, data, None)

    end_time = timeit.default_timer()

    encryption_time = end_time - start_time

    start_time = timeit.default_timer()

    decrypted_data = cipher.decrypt(nonce, ciphertext, None)

    end_time = timeit.default_timer()

    decryption_time = end_time - start_time

    return encryption_time, decryption_time

num_iterations = 1000

total_encryption_time = 0

total_decryption_time = 0

for _ in range(num_iterations):

    encryption_time, decryption_time =

measure_chacha20_poly1305_encryption_decryption_time()

    total_encryption_time += encryption_time

    total_decryption_time += decryption_time

average_encryption_time = total_encryption_time / num_iterations

average_decryption_time = total_decryption_time / num_iterations

print(f"Average Encryption Time for ChaCha20-Poly1305: {average_encryption_time:.6f} seconds")

print(f"Average Decryption Time for ChaCha20-Poly1305: {average_decryption_time:.6f} seconds")

Average Encryption Time for ChaCha20-Poly1305: 0.0000146667 seconds
Average Decryption Time for ChaCha20-Poly1305: 0.0000014 seconds
```

Fig. 1 Python Code For Encryption/Decryption Time of Cacha20-poly1305

Fig.2 Encryption Time For different Encryption Algorithm

A. Decryption Time

Decryption time is the time it takes to decrypt encrypted data, including single pieces and multiple pieces. It provides insight into the overall performance impact of decryption in a given context. In real-time communication or fast data retrieval scenarios, minimizing decryption time is essential. If data is not encrypted after successful authentication, it is useless. Afterwards, The data owner decrypts the contents using the secret key. The average decryption time is used to measure performance, as shown in a table [4]. We utilized the Python code to calculate the average encryption and decryption time for each of the data size taken to measurements.

Table.2 Decryption Time

Data Size	Blowfish	AES-128	AES-192	AES-256	Chacha-20	Chacha20-poly1305
1MB	0.00002	0.00000045	0.0000003833	0.00000035	0.00008	0.000014
10MB	0.00296	0.00010918	0.000106	0.0001144833	0.00047	0.000221967
20MB	0.00349	0.00019098	0.0001984333	0.0002057833	0.00081	0.00042885

40MB	0.00653	0.00043712	0.0004515667	0.0004624167	0.00261	0.000873817
100MB	0.03023	0.00209363	0.0033714167	0.0038070833	0.00341	0.001827033

Fig. 3 Encryption Time For different Decryption Algorithm

The above-mentioned graph shows that the Chacha20-poly1305 algorithm takes less time for the encryption of even larger data sizes. The table and its graphical representation prove the same. The result suggests that Chacha20-poly1305 is the most suitable encryption algorithm for huge data.

Throughput: Throughput is the overall data processing capacity over time, indicating the number of encryption or decryption operations a system can handle within a given period. It is particularly important in encryption scenarios where large volumes of data or high transfer rates are involved. To calculate throughput, use the formula: $\text{Throughput} = \text{Data Size} / \text{Encryption Time}$. This is particularly relevant in network communication, data centers, or backups. For each encryption technique, the throughput is calculated by dividing the 1 MB data size by the encryption time.

Blowfish: 1MB Data Size / 0.00003 seconds encryption time = 33,333.33 Mbps.

AES128: 1MB Data Size/ 0.00000045 seconds encryption time = 2,222,222.22 Mbps.

AES 192: 1MB Data Size/ 0.0000004 seconds encryption time 2,500,000.00 Mbps.

AES 256: 1MB Data size/ 0.00000035 seconds encryption time = 2,857,142.86 Mbps.

Chacha20: 1MB Data Size / 0.00011 seconds encryption Time = 9,090.91 Mbps.

Chacha20-Poly1305:1MB Data Size/ 0.00000146667 seconds encryption time 682,625.68 Mbps.

Table.3 Throughput

Encryption Algorithms	1MB	10MB	20MB	40MB	100MB
Blowfish	33333.33	3424.66	5491.80	5788.32	3424.66
AES-128	2222222.22	91491.22	104771.57	91166.84	47766.19
AES-192	2500000	97402.81	102332.66	91575.08	44997.75
AES-256	2857142.86	89446.68	99668.19	88448.44	47268.94
Chacha-20	9090.91	20000	16000	13986.01	34246.58
Chacha20-poly1305	681818.18	44738.84	45998.40	45996.60	54610.34

Fig. 4 Throughput of different Encryption

Above mention graph[3] summarizes the throughput for each considered encryption algorithm. The figure shows that the throughput of the chacha20-poly1305 algorithm with

higher than chacha20 and Blowfish, but lower than the AES(128,192,256) with 1 MB data size. Again, the throughput of the AES-128 algorithm is lower than the AES-256 and AES-192 algorithm. But as the size of the data increases eventually, it does not look higher. With the data size of 10, 20, and 40MB it is slightly higher, further with the 100 MB data size it looks higher. From the above discussion, we conclude that the throughput of AES is higher than chacha20-poly1305 and the throughput of blowfish and chach20 algorithm is low among these algorithms with 1,10,20,40MB size data but higher with 100MB data. While ChaCha20-Poly1305 may have a slightly lower throughput compared to AES-256 with fewer data sizes, it still offers a very high throughput rate with higher data size. As we know if the throughput increased then power consumption decreased. Therefore, if we prioritize throughput as a performance, in case of security in the cloud, various factors come into play when selecting an encryption algorithm, and throughput is just one of them.

3. COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS

Blowfish: Blowfish is a symmetric-key block cipher designed to provide high security and fast encryption. It operates on 64-bit blocks and supports key sizes from 32 bits to 448 bits. It is sometimes used in cloud environments where symmetric encryption is required for securing data during transmission or storage. It provides a balance between security and performance, making it suitable for various applications.

Advanced Encryption Standard (AES): AES is a symmetric encryption algorithm widely adopted for its security and efficiency. It operates on 128-bit blocks and supports key sizes of 128, 192, or 256 bits. AES is one of the most commonly used encryption algorithms in cloud environments due to its strong security properties and standardized implementation. It is utilized for encrypting data at rest, securing communication channels, and protecting sensitive information stored in the cloud.

ChaCha20: ChaCha20 is a stream cipher designed for high speed and security. It uses a 256-bit key and operates on 64-byte blocks, providing both encryption and authentication through its Poly1305 MAC. ChaCha20 is gaining popularity in cloud environments due to its efficient performance and strong security. It is used for encrypting data in transit, securing communication protocols (e.g., TLS/SSL), and providing authenticated encryption for sensitive information exchanged over networks.

ChaCha20-Poly1305: ChaCha20 is a stream cipher while Poly1305 is a message authentication code (MAC). When used together, they provide authenticated encryption,

ensuring both confidentiality and integrity of data. ChaCha20 encrypts data, scrambling it in a way that only authorized parties with the decryption key can access the original information. Poly1305 generates a cryptographic tag for each message, allowing the recipient to verify that the data hasn't been tampered with during transmission. While ChaCha20-Poly1305 focuses more on confidentiality and integrity, their efficient design contributes indirectly to availability by minimizing computational overhead during encryption and decryption processes. This technique alone is capable to handle three main security concept confidentiality, integrity and availability. It is also useful in the three states of data for instance data-in-use, data-at-transfer and data-at-rest. Additionally, it is often used in combination with other security mechanisms, such as key management practices and access controls, to provide comprehensive protection for big data in the cloud.

Table.4 Comparison of Performance of Encryption Algorithms

Encryption Algorithm	Key length	Performance	Reliability	Remarks
Blowfish	Variable	Average	Measured secure	Key schedule can be slow
AES-128	128 bits	Fast	Very much reliable and widely approved	Average encryption choice for many applications, but not suitable for Big data security.
AES-192	192 bits	Average	Very much reliable	Provides a bit more security than AES-128.
AES-256	256 bits	Slow	Very much reliable	Highest key length, posing enhanced security but slower performance.
Chacha-20	256 bits	Fast	Secure and effectual	Highly used due to speed and security but not suitable for big data because of handling encryption key
Chacha20-poly1305	256 bits	Fast	Very much reliable	better performance and reliable by combining authentication and encryption.

4. RESULT AND DISCUSSIONS

The implementation and comparative evaluation of Blowfish, AES-128, AES-192, AES-256, ChaCha20, and ChaCha20-Poly1305 encryption algorithms for securing big data in cloud computing environments have provided valuable insights into their performance, security, and reliability.

- While Blowfish is known for its simplicity and speed, its performance may be outperformed by newer encryption algorithms such as AES and ChaCha20, mostly for large data sets and modern computing architectures. Its 64-bit block size and susceptibility to certain cryptographic attacks may raise security concerns for big data in cloud-based systems. Blowfish may not be the optimal choice for securing big data due to its limited block size and potential security vulnerabilities.
- AES is widely supported and integrated into various cryptographic libraries and frameworks, making it a practical choice for securing big data in cloud environments. Its flexibility and scalability make it suitable for a wide range of applications. AES-128, AES-192, and AES-256 proved excellent performance in terms of encryption and decryption. AES-128, AES-192, and AES-256 are well-vetted encryption algorithms with strong security properties, offers robust protection against brute-force attacks and other cryptographic threats. AES-256 provided the highest level of security at the expense of slightly higher computational overhead.
- ChaCha20 unveiled performance compared to AES, offering fast encryption and decryption while maintaining strong security properties. Its simple and efficient design makes it well-suited for resource-constrained environments. ChaCha20 and ChaCha20-Poly1305 offer excellent security against known cryptographic attacks. Their use of a 256-bit key ensures high entropy and resistance to brute-force attacks. ChaCha20 and ChaCha20-Poly1305 offer excellent performance and security for data-in-transit making them suitable choices for securing data transfers and communication channels in cloud environments. ChaCha20-Poly1305 combines the ChaCha20 stream cipher with the Poly1305 authenticator, providing both encryption and message authentication capabilities.

5. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE SCOPE

The study on encryption algorithms for securing big data in the cloud has yielded valuable insights into their performance, security, and reliability. The analysis compared algorithms for big data security, with Blowfish showing competitive performance and security properties, especially for smaller key sizes. Blowfish, despite not being as widely used as AES, is a viable alternative encryption algorithm with proven security and performance characteristics for organizations. AES is a robust encryption algorithm with strong performance across key lengths, suitable for encrypting large volumes of big data in the cloud while maintaining high throughput and security. ChaCha20 and ChaCha20-Poly1305 are lightweight, efficient encryption algorithms that offer speed and resistance to side-channel attacks, making them ideal for resource-constrained environments and real-time cloud big data processing tasks.

To be able to ensure long-term security information maintained on cloud platforms, future research must look into encryption techniques as the field of quantum computing evolves. More research on homomorphic methods of encryption must be conducted to enable secure computing on encrypted large volumes while maintaining security and anonymity. Strong key management systems built for massive data environments on cloud computing services are needed to ensure secure actions, storage, and transfer of encryption keys. Use sophisticated threat intelligence and monitoring tools to quickly identify and address changing security risks. By addressing future scope areas, organizations can enhance the security, reliability of their big data in cloud systems, ensuring the confidentiality, integrity and availability of stored data. Cloud-based big data systems combine machine learning and artificial intelligence (AI) for real-time threat detection and prevention. When ML/AI security solutions are integrated with encryption and other conventional safeguards methods, enterprises might develop robust defences for big data as well as infrastructure protection.

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